

PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7560194>

ANNOTATION

The educational process depends on the student's age, psychological and organization taking into account individual circumstances, student's psychological such as improving their condition and coordinating their attitudes towards the lesson, the importance of psychology in the organization of skills is highly appreciated. The purpose of the article is to describe the individual and psychological characteristics of school-children.

KEY WORDS: character, emotions, exopsychic, endopsychic, individual-psychological feature, reflector, temperament, motivational circles.

Interrelationship of biological and social factors in the development of human personality, problems are considered one of the controversial and complex issues in psychology. Especially, children's psychology is complex and pure as they are so young as well as free to do anything.

All mental manifestations of a person are formed during his life. Individual-psychological features of a person are called abilities, temperament, character, emotions, motivational circles are understood. These are psychological characteristics existing in an inseparable way, interdependent, conditioned, to each other in human activity will merge. Taking into account the individual characteristics of people and them. It is of great importance to apply knowledge about social life in practical life plays an important role in the full development of activities and abilities.

Historical process with the social structure of the human personality, which is both a product and a subject at the same time maintaining a biological structure that is located side by side and has equal rights can't stay. Natural conditions of individual development, its physical structure is nervous and endocrine system, advantages and disadvantages in physical structure affects the formation of his individual-psychological features. But biological factors become part of a person's personality and become a social factor and later it will exist in a social form. In the formation of personality, its social and natural features form a unity and as an independent sub-structure of the individual one

cannot be opposed by itself. In psychology, two factors in a person are biological and that there are two main sub-structures formed under the influence of social factors the theory that emphasizes it takes a significant place.

The human person himself is “endopsychic” and it was suggested that it has an “exopsychic” structure. The structure of the personality is small “Endopsychic” breakdown as a structure is similar to a person’s neuro-psychic breakdown, Psychic parts such as the internal mechanism of the human personality that are similar and expresses the interdependence of functions. The exterior of “exopsychia” in relation to the environment, that is, no matter how the person is, to the relation of violations that may occur and are against the Person is defined in relation to all. “Endopsychics” tendency, memory thinking and others such as imagination, willpower, susceptibility to external influences traits, and "exopsychism" refers to the system of human relations and its experience, for instance his interests, ideals, inclinations, superior feelings, includes formed knowledge and other signs. Natural basis “endopsychic” is determined by the social factor, and “exopsychic” by the biological aspect depends.

The importance of biological and social factors in the formation of personality is a number psychologists have consistently studied in their scientific work, and some of them have thought and we bring their views.

American psychologist S. Hall Haeckel's law of evolution to psychology moved. According to him, "heredity" repeats phylogeny in onogeny. A scientist according to the interpretation, infancy is nothing more than a stage of development characteristic of animals, childhood and to the time of ancient people whose main occupation was hunting and fishing fits exactly.

Primary students are masters of play. One of the most important indicators of a species’ intelligence is the behavior of its young – all intelligent animals play (Ackerman, 1999). Primary learners are at an age where learning capacity and brain development are at their peak, and nature has given them the drive to maximize that power with its best learning tool – play. It is no surprise that children prefer acting and interacting to listening passively. It’s how they are designed. Play is the context within which primary students can develop vital skills that are harder to practice in more structured formats – complex decision-making, leadership, and executive functioning. It invites the “having of wonderful ideas.” Play also builds the foundation for abstract representational thinking – a rag on a stick becomes a flag, just as a set of squiggles on a page stands for a word. Play encourages children to create and narrate their own

worlds, grapple with the challenges most urgent to them, and gain experience negotiating alliances, roles, and strategies with their peers. Encouraging play in the classroom, and strategically harnessing its power for specific learning purposes allows for authentic engagement and deep learning opportunities for our youngest students. As Albert Einstein told, "Play is the highest form of research" and I am strongly agree with this idea according to my experience all children are playful. Everytime they want to play games, even when they are learning something. So, to my perspective, teachers should be aware of playing games and types of games which are appropriate to utilize during the lesson.

Moreover, children are good observers and imitators. Primary students seek to belong. More important than any curriculum or instruction is a culture of love, warmth, and beauty. Children are keen observers of the environment and adult behavior - what they see when they walk into the classroom, how they are greeted by their teacher and classmates, and how they perceive social interactions all have a profound effect on their sense of belonging (Howard, 2006). A strong relationship with an adult in the classroom is especially critical for young students to feel safe. The teacher's love, care, and thoughtfulness are evident in the organization of the classroom, the display of beautiful student work, and the quality of the materials for expression, learning, and play. Classroom communities celebrating acts of kindness and respectfully resolving conflict reinforce a sense of justice and good will. Singing and dancing together create a language of unity that young children understand - a sense of safety in a community that is greater than any individual member. Feeling secure in a kind and beautiful classroom creates a strong inner foundation for the development of young children's academic and relational character.

With him by taking into account the individual-psychological features of the person interpersonal communication is important. In addition, each ability to perceive and understand the world and people in a unique way that they ensure making less mistakes in the process of communication. For example, modesty, thoughtfulness, looking at the inner world of others by their words and actions cognitive ability and others are among them.

In conclusion, A child has two spheres of social relations: "child - adults" and "child - children". These systems are related to gaming activities. Relationships exist in parallel and are not hierarchical relationships. At the primary school age, the game does not disappear, it takes new forms and new content. Typical games for children of primary school age are rules that regulate the combination of forces in a team of children playing (role-playing games). Mental development.

Intuition, perception. The perception of a young student is determined by the specific features of the subject: it is not the main thing to be noticed, but something that catches the eye, often the perception is limited only to recognizing the subject and then naming it. The perceived situation mediates mental operations to a lesser extent than in preschoolers.

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